

LITERARY ANALYSIS OF IMAGE AND IMAGERY

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Abstract

In the eighteenth century one theory of ‘imagination’ was a faculty for visualization, so literature was often regarded as a medium which promoted visual responses in the reader: that is to say, “images”. The term image is described variously by dictionaries, encyclopedias and other literary books. And in some nations` literature the meaning of the word image or imagery is used to make analysis of characters, objects. The writing includes information about how the term came up and which writers used in what way.

Key words: imagination, image, imagery, literature, dictionary, characters, objects

We know that an image is a mental picture. It is abstract and merely conceived in the mind. The etymology of the word tells about its association in Latin with “statue” “idol” or “figure” suggesting “likeness” and “imitation”. The inability of the human mind to accurately recall all the details of a picture reflects the imitative aspect of the image. In fact, there are varying degrees of fidelity and vividness in a mental image depending on the cognitive abilities of the person in question.¹

The terms *image* and *imagery* have many connotations and meanings. Imagery as a general term covers the use of language to represent objects, actions, feelings, thoughts, ideas, states of mind and any sensory or extra-sensory experience. An ‘image’ does not necessarily mean a mental picture. In the first place we may

¹ Peter E. Morris and Peter J. Hampson - Imagery and consciousness. p. 7

distinguish between the literal, the perceptual and the conceptual. These lines from Robert Lowell’s “Our Lady of Walsingham” illustrate the basic differences:

There once the penitents took off their shoes
And then walked barefoot the remaining mile.
And the small trees, a stream and hedgerows file
Slowly along the munching English lane.
Like cows to the old shrine, until you lose
Track of your dragging pain.
The stream flows down under the druid tree,
Shiloah’s whirlpools gurgle and make glad
The castle of God.

The first two lines are a literal image without figurative language which may or may not convey a visual image also. The phrase ‘hedgerows file slowly’ is a perceptual image because of the metaphorical use of the word ‘file’. The phrase ‘castle of God’ is conceptual. One can hardly visualize it but one may have an idea of it.

Many *images* (but by no means all) are conveyed by figurative language, as in metaphor, simile, synecdoche, onomatopoeia and metonymy. An image may be visual - pertaining to the eye, olfactory - smell, tactile - touch, auditory - hearing, gustatory - taste, abstract (in which case it will appeal to what may be described as the intellect) and kinesthetic - pertaining to the sense of movement and bodily effort.²

These lines from Peter Redgrove’s “Lazarus and the Sea” contain all these kinds of image:

The tide of my death came whispering like this
Soiling my body with its tireless voice.
I scented the antique moistures when they sharpened
The air of my room, made the rough wood of my bed, (most dear).

² J.A. Cuddon – The Penguin Dictionary of Literary. p.413-415

Standing out like roots in my tall grave.
They slopped in my mouth and entered my plaited blood
Quietened my jolting breath with a soft argument
Of such measured insistence, untied the great knot of my heart.
They spread like whispered conversations
Through all the numbed rippling tissues radiated
Like a tree for thirty years from the still centre
Of my salt ovum. But this calm dissolution
Came after my agreement to the necessity of it;
Where before it was a storm over red fields
Pocked with the rain and the wheat furrowed
With wind, then it was the drifting of smoke
From a fire of the wood, damp with sweat,
Fallen in the storm. '

It is often the case that an image is not exclusively one thing or another; they overlap and intermingle and thus combine. Thus, the kinesthetic may also be visual.

In this quotation the first two lines are clearly auditory, but the use of the word 'soiling' may suggest the tactile; on the other hand, for some, the word may have olfactory associations. The third line is olfactory. In the fourth and fifth lines we have a combination of the tactile and visual. The sixth line intermingles the tactile, olfactory and gustatory. The phrases 'quietened my jolting breath' and 'through all the numbed rippling tissues' are kinesthetic, but are also visual and tactile. 'But this calm dissolution/Came after my agreement to the necessity of it;' is abstract. 'Untied the great knot of my heart' is visual- cum-kinesthetic. The other images in the poem fall readily into one of the categories mentioned.

The list of used literature:

1. Peter E. Morris and Peter J. Hampson - Imagery and consciousness. p. 7
2. J.A. Cuddon – The Penguin Dictionary of Literary. p.413-415
3. <https://www.grin.com/document/181933>